

Appendix A. Description of the results structure

• Time and references

- `results.t`: time vector of the simulation horizon [s].
- `results.refs`: structure or matrix collecting the reference trajectories used by the controllers (e.g., setpoints for pH, DO, and temperature).

• Measured and reported process variables

- `results.pH`: pH signal (dimensionless).
- `results.DO`: dissolved oxygen in percent saturation [%].
- `results.T`: bulk reactor temperature [°C].
- `results.X_gL`: biomass concentration expressed in g L^{-1} .
- `results.Depth`: culture depth [m], computed from volume and geometry.

• Control commands and effective flow rates

- `results.Qair_cmd`: air injection command (controller output), before actuator limits are applied.
- `results.QCO2_cmd`: CO₂ injection command.
- `results.Qair_del`: delivered air flow rate after saturation and actuator constraints [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$].
- `results.QCO2_del`: delivered CO₂ flow rate [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$].
- `results.Qd`: dilution inflow effectively used in the model [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$].
- `results.Qh`: harvesting outflow effectively used in the model [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$].

• Cumulative gas usage and biomass metrics

- `results.cum_air_L`: cumulative volume of air injected over time [L].
- `results.cum_CO2_L`: cumulative volume of CO₂ injected [L].
- `results.cum_harv_g`: cumulative harvested biomass [g].
- `results.total_air_L`: total air consumption over the entire horizon [L].

- `results.total_CO2_L`: total CO₂ consumption [L].

• Key performance indicators (KPIs)

- `results.gain_g`: net biomass gain between the initial and final time [g].
- `results.acumm_rel`: relative biomass accumulation index (dimensionless), comparing final and initial biomass inventories.
- `results.prod_g`: total biomass produced (gross production) [g].
- `results.prod_areal_gm2_day`: areal productivity [$\text{g m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$].
- `results.harv_total_g`: total harvested biomass [g].
- `results.harv_frac`: fraction of produced biomass that is effectively harvested (dimensionless).
- `results.harv_prod_areal_gm2_day`: areal productivity associated with the harvested biomass [$\text{g m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$].

• Biological rates and limitation factors

- `results.mu_I`: light limitation factor μ_I .
- `results.mu_T`: temperature limitation factor μ_T .
- `results.mu_pH`: pH limitation factor μ_{pH} .
- `results.mu_DO`: DO inhibition term μ_{DO} .
- `results.P`: gross photosynthetic rate P [d^{-1} or s^{-1} , depending on model parametrization].
- `results.mu`: net specific growth rate μ_g [d^{-1} or s^{-1}].
- `results.m`: maintenance/respiration rate m [d^{-1} or s^{-1}].

• Carbonate system and cations

- `results.DIC`: dissolved inorganic carbon concentration [mol m^{-3}].
- `results.Cat`: strong cation concentration [mol m^{-3}].
- `results.HCO3`: bicarbonate concentration HCO_3^- [mol m^{-3}].
- `results.CO3`: carbonate concentration CO_3^{2-} [mol m^{-3}].
- `results.CO2`: dissolved CO₂ concentration [mol m^{-3}].

- **Heat-exchanger substructure**

- `results.HX.Qw_m3s`: water flow rate through the spiral heat exchanger [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$].
- `results.HX.Tin_C`: inlet water temperature to the heat exchanger [$^{\circ}\text{C}$].
- `results.HX.Tout_C`: outlet water temperature from the heat exchanger [$^{\circ}\text{C}$].
- `results.HX.UA_WK`: overall heat-transfer coefficient times area, UA [W K^{-1}].
- `results.HX.Q_W`: instantaneous heat flux exchanged with the culture, Q_{HX} [W].
- `results.HX.limits`: structure containing actuator limits for the heat-exchanger loop: `Qw_min`, `Qw_max`, `Tin_min`, and `Tin_max`.